

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-6-95-OJH-2% 40 05 ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20231025
Vial:	82	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400 40 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	695
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	280.0nm
Run Time:	70.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 280.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/25/2023 6:34:53 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/25/2023 10:15:59 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	18.953	3282275	28.26	110867
2	25.232	3092370	26.62	71474
3	27.027	2601536	22.40	54157
4	30.194	2638481	22.72	48521

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-6-83-OJH-2% 40 05 ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	83	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400 40 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	683
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	280.0nm
Run Time:	65.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 280.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/25/2023 7:43:45 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/25/2023 10:17:48 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	18.856	7245780	90.58	239765
2	25.185	49853	0.62	1422
3	26.988	431049	5.39	9064
4	30.101	272837	3.41	5573